

1 **Supplementary Material from: Assessing the best hour to start the day: an appraisal**
2 **of Daylight Saving Time**

3 José María Martín-Olalla

4 *Universidad de Sevilla, Facultad de Física, Departamento de Física de la Materia Condensada, ES41012 Sevilla, Spain**

5 Jorge Mira

6 *Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, Facultade de Física,*

7 *Departamento de Física Aplicada and iMATUS, ES15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain†*

8 (Received 1 May 2024; Revised 7 November 2024; Accepted 4 December 2024; Published 19 March 2025)

9 This version is published in zenodo doi:10.5281/zenodo.15044181

10 Keywords: DST; summer time; society; latitude; sleep deprivation; spring transition; Europe; America;
11 season; motor vehicle accidents; myocardial infarction

-
- 12 [1] M. Sani, R. Refinetti, G. Jean-Louis, S. R. Pandi- 19 Kuznetsova, N. B. Petrova, V. D. Timonin, S. N. Kolome-
13 Perumal, R. A. Durazo-Arvizu, L. R. Dugas, R. Kafensz- 20 ichuk, I. A. Vinogradova, M. S. Kovyazina, N. A.
14 tok, P. Bovet, T. E. Forrester, E. V. Lambert, J. Plange- 21 Khokhlov, A. L. Kosova, and O. N. Kasyanova, Seven-year
15 Rhule, and A. Luke, Daily activity patterns of 2316 men 22 survey of sleep timing in russian children and adolescents:
16 and women from five countries differing in socioeconomic 23 chronic 1-h forward transition of social clock is associated
17 development, *Chronobiology International* **32**, 650 (2015). 24 with increased social jetlag and winter pattern of mood
18 [2] M. F. Borisenkov, T. A. Tserne, A. S. Panev, E. S. 25 seasonality, *Chronobiology International* **48**, 3 (2017).

* olalla@us.es; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3750-9113>;
<https://ror.org/03yxnp24>

† jorge.mira@usc.es; <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6024-6294>;
<https://ror.org/030eybx10>

Figure S1. The Earth aligned to the orbital axis at the two solstices. View point looks at the 75th meridian West of the prime meridian (11:00 UTC) and at the Equator; the incoming solar radiation strike horizontally right to left and the terminator line is rendered upright. The solar radiation is drawn on the plane that intersects the 15th meridian East ($-75^\circ + 90^\circ = 15^\circ$), where noon is occurring. The annotations show ray (sun) elevation (θ , the complementary angle of the incidence angle) in parenthesis and with the sine of this angle, which sets the efficiency of the solar radiation. They are function of latitude only. The top panel (December) shows the delay of sunrise time with latitude in the Northern hemisphere, and a low $\sin \theta$ in this hemisphere. The bottom panel (June) shows the advance of sunrise time in the Northern hemisphere, and an insolation $\sin \theta$ which is characteristically Tropical below 47° . Borders were obtained from <https://naturalearth.com>; a 2D day and night world map was produced with `gnuplot`, white dots in the night map come from populated places in <https://www.geonames.org>; the projection and the terminator line was rendered by `xplanet`; the pictures were annotated with `TikZ`.

Figure S2. The association of the acrophase —time of activity peak— and winter sunrise. Sani *et al.* [1, Figure 3] reported the acrophase vs latitude in five countries differing in socioeconomic development (solid circles, local time) and the regression line (solid, $r = 0.92$; $p = 0.02$). Here we add the acrophase mean solar time (open circles) and a one-hour width band strip showing (dashed lines) SRW plus an offset of 6.7 h (low bound) and 7.7 h (high bound) to highlight that the delay in the acrophase follows the delay in SRW. Labels display iso-3166 alpha-3 code for Ghana (GHA), Seychelles (SYC), Jamaica (JAM), South Africa (ZAF) and United States of America (USA). Data were digitized by WebPlotDigitizer <https://automeris.io/> ©Autonumeris LLC.

Figure S3. The bimodal, two-season scheme designed by seasonal clock regulations. Top, the yearly evolution of the solar declination (dashed) —the latitude of the subsolar point, where the solar radiation impacts with 100% efficiency and no shadow is cast— and the bimodal, two-season sketch (solid): at high enough distance to the Equator, either season is light (spring-summer) on one hemisphere and dark (autumn-winter) on the opposite hemisphere. Bottom, the yearly evolution of sunrise time at 40°N (dashed line), and the bimodal, equivalent model (thick line) set by clock regulations: a bimodal sunrise time (SRW in autumn-winter and SRW^- in spring-summer) that sets a bimodal timing (phase) of human activity through bimodal clocks. For this figure solar sunrise is set at the upper limb of the sun and atmospheric refraction is considered so that SRW is 07:20, six minutes earlier than Figure 1 and Figure 2 in the manuscript. The solar declination was computed by `xplanet` and the equation of time by Darin Koblick's script for MathWorks® available at <https://es.mathworks.com/matlabcentral/fileexchange/32793-equation-of-time>.

Figure S4. Borisenkov *et al.* [2] analysed sleep timing in Russian children and adolescent (scholars). Table 1 in the cited study lists the locations and their geographical coordinates. Key 1: Moscow; 2: Saint-Petersburg; 3: Petrozavodsk; 4: Apatity; 5: Murmansk; 6: Mutnitsa; 7: Kazhym; 8: Obyachevo; 9: Syktyvkar; 10: Ust-Kulom; 11: Timsher; 12: Izhma; 13: Inta and 14: Vorkuta. The map (see also Figure 1 in the cited study) locates winter sunrise time (SRW) expressed as Moscow Time: MSK=UTC+03. Table 4 in the cited study reports local school start times as 08:30 MSK. The golden shaded area shows regions with clocks set to MSK currently. Until 2011, clocks were seasonally regulated. From 2011 to 2014 perennial DST (MSK=UTC+04) was tested. Since, perennial MSK is in use. Borders were obtained from <https://naturalearth.com>